

Rheological characterization of clay–refractory waste composites for direct ink writing of ceramic structures

Jiří Rozbroj^a, David Žurovec^a, Jakub Hlosta^{a,*}, Michaela Topinková^b,
Hana Ovčáčiková^b, Jan Diviš^a, Kamila Pokorná^a, Jan Nečas^a, Jiří Zegzulka^a

^a VSB-Technical University of Ostrava, Faculty of Mining and Geology, Department of Mining Engineering and Safety, 17. listopadu 15/2172, 708 00 Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic

^b VSB-Technical University of Ostrava, Faculty of Materials Science and Technology, Department of Thermal Engineering, 17. listopadu 15/2172, 708 00 Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Direct ink writing (DIW)
Rheology
Particles
Refractory ceramics
Waste materials
Circular economy

ABSTRACT

In the context of the circular economy and raw material sustainability, it is essential to explore alternative raw materials for the development of formulations with optimized physical and mechanical properties. This study focused on the rheological characterization of refractory ceramic waste blended with clay, aiming to optimize compositions for 3D printing. A mixture exhibiting the highest strength and resistance to shear stress was identified, making it a promising candidate for use in complex structural components. Mixtures with lower strength proved suitable for less demanding applications with simpler geometries. The presence of finer particles and lower bulk density of the filler led to increased viscosity and critical shear stress, contributing to higher mechanical stability. In contrast, mixtures with higher bulk density exhibited lower viscosity and reduced resistance to mechanical loading, despite demonstrating higher elasticity within the linear viscoelastic region. These findings represent a significant contribution to the effective selection and design of refractory ceramic formulations for additive manufacturing, tailored to the specific functional requirements of targeted applications. The research also demonstrated the feasibility of using waste-derived materials as feedstock for Direct Ink Writing (DIW) 3D printing of refractory ceramics, supporting both material circularity and sustainable manufacturing practices.

1. Introduction

Rheology of ceramic mixtures intended for 3D printing plays a crucial role in optimizing their processability, extrusion behaviour, and layer stability [1–3]. Key parameters affecting the printability of these pastes include particle size and size distribution, liquid phase content, and the presence of additives or binders, all of which collectively govern the flow and mechanical behaviour of the material during and after printing [4–6]. The particle size distribution has a direct influence on viscosity, yield stress, shear-thinning behaviour, and the ability to maintain structural stability during layer stacking.

Fine particles contribute to enhanced plasticity and cohesion, facilitating shaping and improving the interlayer adhesion of extruded structures. However, a higher proportion of fine particles can result in

increased viscosity [7,8] and shear stress, which may negatively affect the continuity of extrusion. Conversely, the presence of coarser particles may reduce viscosity while maintaining higher yield stress levels [9]. An optimal particle size distribution is therefore essential for achieving the desired rheological characteristics of ceramic pastes [10].

For efficient Direct Ink Writing (DIW) of ceramics, it is essential that the paste exhibits optimal rheological properties [11]. One of the critical characteristics is shear-thinning behaviour [11–14], where the viscosity decreases with increasing shear stress, enabling a smooth and continuous flow during extrusion. After deposition, however, the material must rapidly recover its internal structure, a property known as thixotropy, to preserve the geometric integrity of the printed layers and prevent deformation under self-weight or due to subsequent layers [15–17]. Additionally, the storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') play

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: jiri.rozbroj@vsb.cz (J. Rozbroj), david.zurovec@vsb.cz (D. Žurovec), jakub.hlosta@vsb.cz (J. Hlosta), michaela.topinkova@vsb.cz (M. Topinková), hana.ovcackikova@vsb.cz (H. Ovčáčiková), jan.divis@vsb.cz (J. Diviš), kamila.pokorna@vsb.cz (K. Pokorná), jan.necas@vsb.cz (J. Nečas), jiri.zegzulka@vsb.cz (J. Zegzulka).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceram.2025.100850>

Received 22 July 2025; Received in revised form 12 September 2025; Accepted 14 September 2025

Available online 14 September 2025

2666-5395/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd on behalf of European Ceramic Society. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

important roles in characterizing the viscoelastic response of the material [18–20]. The crossover point of these moduli indicates the onset of flow. A paste with excessively high yield stress may be difficult to extrude, while one with low yield stress may undesirably spread after deposition [21–24].

Advanced rheological characterization methods, typically conducted using rotational rheometers, enable the determination of flow curves, viscoelasticity, and thixotropic recovery. Measurement of dynamic rheological parameters, such as storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G''), provides insights into the mechanical stability of the material and its ability to maintain structural integrity post-extrusion. Rheological analysis thus facilitates the optimization of paste formulations by adjusting the ratio of solids, binders, and liquid phase, ultimately leading to improved printability and higher quality of the final ceramic components [25–33].

The field of silicate materials encompasses a wide range of heterogeneous materials with varying chemical compositions, microstructures, and properties. Among them are refractory ceramics derived as industrial waste, particularly from biomass combustion boilers and fireplace inserts. When added to clay-based formulations, these materials can alter the viscosity, thixotropy, and strength of the resulting structures, while simultaneously contributing to waste recycling and reducing the environmental impact of ceramic manufacturing. Refractory materials can be classified as heterogeneous ceramics composed primarily of six oxides: SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , MgO , CaO , Cr_2O_3 , and ZrO . Their primary function is to protect furnace linings from high temperatures, mechanical stress, and chemical corrosion. A major issue affecting the durability of refractory linings is corrosion [34], which generates refractory waste, requiring periodic replacement. In biomass combustion systems, the refractory linings are typically based on the SiO_2 – Al_2O_3 system. These materials can be further classified based on their Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 content into several categories: high-alumina (HA, 45–98 % Al_2O_3), fireclay (FC, 30–45 % Al_2O_3), low-fireclay (LF, 10–30 % Al_2O_3), silica–semi-silica (SS, 85–93 % SiO_2), and silica (SL, >93 % SiO_2) [35,36].

This study focuses on the rheological analysis of clay-based mixtures modified with waste refractory ceramics, with the primary objective of evaluating their suitability for extrusion-based 3D printing in the context of material sustainability and circular economy principles. Key rheological parameters influencing printability, layer stability, and mechanical properties of the final structures will be investigated. The results will aid in identifying optimal formulations for effective use in the additive manufacturing of ceramic components.

2. Methods

2.1. Materials

For the study of the rheological properties of refractory materials for 3D printing, four types of silicate ceramics were utilized. The first component was a clay matrix (labelled as IBV), combined with three types of waste refractory materials (labelled as RW1, RW2, and RW3). The base matrix of the ceramic mixture was formed by the IBV clay, which is sourced from the Nová Ves–Suchá deposit in the Czech Republic. This is a white porous clay that belongs to the kaolinitic clay group, characterized by a low content of free SiO_2 and mica. During firing, its original colour transforms into a bright white. This clay exhibits high porosity in the ceramic body, excellent refractoriness in the range of 1730–1760 °C, and a sintering temperature of at least 1450 °C. It was supplied in powdered form with a particle size range of 0–2.5 mm. According to the technical datasheet, the drying shrinkage is approximately 3–5%. The clay serves as the primary component of the mixture due to its plasticity, which is essential for shaping during the 3D printing process. Its mineralogical composition (kaolinite, illite, montmorillonite) influences the rheological behaviour and mechanical properties of the cured material. The chemical compositions of the IBV clay and the three types of refractory waste (RW1–RW3) are provided in Table 1.

Table 1

Chemical composition of clay matrix (IBV) and refractory waste materials (RW1–3).

Oxides (wt%)	IBV	RW1	RW2	RW3
Na ₂ O	0.15	0.33	0.34	0.20
MgO	0.29	-	-	0.23
Al ₂ O ₃	36.10	57.87	95.54	38.50
SiO ₂	45.50	39.55	2.93	52.56
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.95	1.10	0.96	3.31
K ₂ O	3.68	0.57	0.02	1.99
CaO	0.23	0.12	0.05	0.44
P ₂ O ₅	-	0.8	-	0.8
SO ₃	-	-	-	-
TiO ₂	1.22	0.24	-	2.26
ZrO ₂	-	-	-	0.09
MnO	-	-	-	0.02
NiO	-	-	-	0.03
LOI	10.55	-	-	0.13

Refractory wastes RW1 and RW2 were classified as high-alumina (HA) refractories, defined by Al_2O_3 contents exceeding 45%, with application temperatures up to 1700 °C. These are shaped refractory materials with apparent porosity up to 18%, based on sillimanite/andalusite and bonded via a chemical–ceramic matrix. In contrast, RW3 falls into the category of fireclay (FC) refractories, as its Al_2O_3 content ranges between 30–40%, confirming its classification. This chamotte-based material is intended for use at temperatures of 1400–1500 °C, typically in furnace linings, boilers, or incinerators.

Fig. 1 presents the X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) patterns of crystalline phases identified in the natural clay IBV and the three types of refractory waste materials (RW1–RW3). The XRPD pattern of the IBV clay, as shown in Fig. 1, confirms that the material primarily consists of kaolinite ($\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_4$) and muscovite ($\text{H}_2\text{Al}_2(\text{SiO}_4)_3$) as the main clay minerals, with quartz (SiO_2) and minor anatase (TiO_2) present as accessory phases. The sharp and well-defined diffraction peaks indicate a high degree of crystallinity, especially for quartz and kaolinite. Kaolinite is identified by its characteristic reflections at $2\theta \approx 12.4^\circ$, 24.9° , and 35° , which are indicative of a well-ordered crystalline structure. Muscovite, present in moderate quantities, is recognized by notable peaks near $2\theta \approx 8.8^\circ$, 19.8° , and 26.6° .

The XRPD pattern of the RW1 sample reveals a highly crystalline structure, dominated by corundum ($\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$), evidenced by sharp, high-intensity peaks at $2\theta \approx 30.1^\circ$, 43.3° , and 52.5° . Additionally, the presence of mullite ($3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$) is confirmed by characteristic peaks at $2\theta \approx 16.4^\circ$, 31.0° , and 41.8° , further verifying the high-alumina nature of the refractory waste. Minor phases such as quartz (SiO_2), moissanite (SiC)—identified by low-intensity peaks near $2\theta \approx 43^\circ$ and 45° —and andalusite (Al_2SiO_5), with reflections observed at approximately $2\theta \approx 18^\circ$, 37° , and 48° , provide additional evidence of the material's complex thermal and chemical transformation history.

The XRPD pattern of the RW2 sample indicates a highly crystalline structure, characterized by sharp and intense diffraction peaks. The RW2 material is composed almost entirely of corundum ($\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$), with prominent peaks located at $2\theta \approx 30^\circ$, 42° , 51° , and 68° . The absence of additional crystalline phases suggests that RW2 represents a high-purity alumina material, likely originating from refractory ceramic waste with minimal contamination or phase transformation.

The XRPD pattern of the RW3 sample reveals the presence of multiple crystalline phases. Characteristic reflections of mullite ($3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$) are observed near $2\theta \approx 16.4^\circ$, 30° , and 40.8° , indicating its role as a primary phase. Unreacted silica appears as quartz (SiO_2), with peaks at $2\theta \approx 31^\circ$, while cristobalite (SiO_2)—a high-temperature polymorph of silica formed above 1470 °C—is identified by its reflection at $2\theta \approx 25^\circ$. Additionally, rutile (TiO_2) is present, as evidenced by peaks at approximately $2\theta \approx 32.1^\circ$ and 41.2° , suggesting the presence of titanium-bearing components likely formed or stabilized during high-temperature processing.

Fig. 1. X-ray powder diffraction pattern; (a) IBV, (b) RW1, (c) RW2, (d) RW3.

2.2. Samples preparation

The advantage of the clay component lies in its plasticity, which results from its structural units. In this formulation, the refractory additive is intended to serve as the structural backbone of the material, enhancing the mechanical properties of the 3D-printed ceramic after firing. Water functions as the dispersion medium and significantly influences the processability of the mixture, its flow behaviour, and the cohesion during layer deposition in the 3D printing process. The ratio of solid particles to water determines the mixture's plasticity, yield stress, and the rate at which it sets after extrusion.

The overall composition of the mixture affects not only printability but also the mechanical and microstructural properties of the final ceramic object. Therefore, formulation optimization is essential to ensure good extrusion behaviour, layer stability, and sufficient strength after drying or firing. Table 2 summarizes the weight ratios of the tested mixtures and their bulk densities. The mixture ratio of solid clay/solid refractory waste/water was selected based on preliminary trials and previous experience with similar clay-based pastes for extrusion. The objective was to achieve a workable balance between extrudability and structural stability immediately after deposition. The amount of mixing water was subsequently optimized to achieve a suitable rheological consistency of the paste and ensure its processability during extrusion. Increasing the water content above the chosen level resulted in excessive viscosity reduction and a loss of structural stability, whereas lowering the water content required a significantly higher extrusion pressure and reduced the compactness of the extruded material.

2.3. Particles

For the analysis of individual material components, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and laser diffraction granulometry were employed. Fig. 2 shows particle size distribution and SEM images of the particles at a magnification of $2000 \times$ with a scale bar of $40 \mu\text{m}$ (IBV) and $130 \times$ with a scale bar of $500 \mu\text{m}$ (RW1–3). The morphology of particles was analysed by the scanning electron microscope SEM/EDAX QUANTA 450 FEG (FEI, Hillsboro, USA). For granulometric analysis, particle size distribution was measured using the Mastersizer 3000 (Malvern Panalytical, Worcestershire, UK). Measurements were conducted on dry samples and their dry mixtures using the dry dispersion method, with air as the carrier medium. The method is based on the principle of laser diffraction, where a laser beam passes through the dispersed sample, and light is scattered depending on particle size. The detector system records the intensity and angle of the scattered light, which the software uses to calculate the particle size distribution.

2.4. Rheology

Rheological measurements were performed using a HAAKE MARS iQ Air Rotational Rheometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA) at a temperature of 23°C , equipped with serrated parallel plates ($\varnothing 25 \text{ mm}$, gap = 3 mm). The shear-thinning behaviour of the material was characterized using a Rotation Ramp test in Control Rate mode, with a shear rate range from $4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$ up to the point of sample failure. The resulting flow curves were fitted using the Power Law model, where the parameter a represents the scaling factor, b is the power-law exponent, and r denotes the correlation coefficient indicating

Table 2
Composition of tested mixtures and bulk density of their components.

Mixture	Weight Ratio	Component	Bulk Density ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)
IBV+RW1+H2O	1 + 1 + 0.8	RW1	1 669
IBV+RW2+H2O	1 + 1 + 0.8	RW2	1 955
IBV+RW3+H2O	1 + 1 + 0.8	RW3	1 108
IBV+H2O	1 + 0.565	IBV	611

the quality of the fit.

The viscoelastic properties of the materials were evaluated using an Oscillatory Amplitude Sweep test (frequency = 1 Hz , shear stress τ ranging from 1 Pa to the point of structural failure), which allowed determination of the storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G''). This test is a key method for characterizing the complex rheological behaviour of materials designed for 3D printing, particularly ceramic pastes and suspensions. It identifies the conditions under which the material behaves more like a fluid ($G'' > G'$) or more like a solid ($G' > G''$).

By determining both moduli, it is possible to assess the material's maximum strength, the linear viscoelastic region (LVR)—where the response remains linear to applied stress—and the critical point ($G' = G''$), which marks the transition to viscous flow or the collapse of the internal structure. Following the DIN 51,810–2 standard with a 5 % plateau tolerance, the end of LVR for both shear stress and shear rate were determined.

2.5. DIW 3D printing

Proper adjustment of printing parameters is critical for achieving optimal accuracy, stability, and quality of the final ceramic structure. Key parameters include the printing speed, which influences extrusion continuity and interlayer adhesion—excessive speed may lead to irregular material flow and deformation, while too low a speed can result in over-deposition and loss of detail. The nozzle diameter determines resolution and affects the overall flow rate of the paste; commonly used diameters range from 0.8 to 2 mm . Smaller nozzles enable finer detail resolution but require more precise rheological control. The layer height typically ranges between 0.5 and 1 mm , depending on the viscosity of the material and the desired structural strength—thinner layers improve accuracy and surface finish, whereas thicker layers accelerate the printing process. Another important factor is the extrusion pressure, which must be sufficient to ensure continuous material output, yet not so high as to cause excessive over-extrusion or uneven layer deposition. The optimal setup of these parameters depends on the composition of the ceramic paste, its rheological behaviour, and the required resolution of the final printed object.

The stability of the printed ceramic structure is influenced by the rheological properties of the paste, the printing parameters, and the interactions between successive layers. A key factor is the thixotropy of the material, which allows sufficient viscosity reduction during extrusion while ensuring rapid structural recovery after deposition to prevent unwanted deformation. Interlayer strength and cohesion are determined not only by the composition of the paste (the ratio of solids, binders, and liquid phase) but also by the drying rate and shrinkage behaviour during drying. If the material exhibits too low a yield stress, it may flow undesirably and lose shape fidelity, whereas an excessively viscous paste may cause interruptions in extrusion and weak interlayer bonding.

Stability assessment includes the analysis of mechanical properties of the printed object before and after drying, along with visual inspection for deformation, layer integrity, and potential shrinkage—all of which can significantly impact the overall quality of the final ceramic product.

The materials were tested in the laboratory at an ambient temperature of 23°C , which also corresponds to the conditions under which the printing process will be performed. At elevated temperatures, accelerated drying of the paste occurs, which does not provide fully optimal conditions for extrusion. While higher temperatures may increase viscosity and complicate extrusion, they also contribute to improved stiffness and deformation resistance after layer deposition. Controlled temperature adjustment could thus represent a potential strategy for further optimization of the DIW printing process. For example, a lower temperature near the nozzle could facilitate extrusion, while a slightly elevated substrate or chamber temperature could enable faster stabilization of the deposited layers. This will be the subject of further research, along with the direct influence of rheological properties on printability and the printing process.

Fig. 2. Particle size distribution and SEM images; (a) IBV, (b) RW1, (c) RW2, (d) RW3.

3. Results

3.1. Particle size distribution and morphology

Fig. 2(a) depicts the IBV component, consisting mainly of smaller particles with a few larger, irregularly shaped ones. The surface appears relatively compact, with a low degree of fragmentation. Fig. 2(b)- RW1 clearly shows larger, sharply angular particles with pronounced edges. The material appears coarser and less cohesive compared to Fig. 2(a). Fig. 1(c)- RW3 presents a combination of rounded and angular particles of varying sizes, with a surface that appears more fragmented and heterogeneous. Fig. 2(d)- RW2 shows a structure like RW3, but with finer and more dispersed particles. Smaller particles are seen filling the voids between larger ones. Based on microscopic observations, particle morphology was assessed for each sample. The materials used exhibit very similar particle shapes, with predominantly angular particles across a wide granulometric distribution range.

The measured data (Table 3) include the median particle size (d_{50}), as well as the lower (d_{10}) and upper (d_{90}) size distribution limits, providing fundamental information about the granulometric characteristics of the studied materials. These results were used to describe the composition of the mixtures for 3D printing, with a focus on identifying suitable particle size distributions to ensure optimal printability and desirable mechanical properties of the final ceramic objects. These parameters made it possible to assess the homogeneity of individual samples and the presence of fine or coarse particles. For a comprehensive view of the particle size distribution characteristics, cumulative curves are the key to predicting the behaviour of the material in various 3D printing processes.

The particle size distribution analysis of ceramic mixtures intended for 3D printing reveals notable differences between the tested formulations. The mixtures IBV+RW1, IBV+RW2, and IBV+RW3 exhibit similar values of d_{10} (3.83–4.00 μm) and d_{90} (30.3–36.4 μm), indicating a relatively fine particle fraction. In contrast, the IBV shows significantly lower values for d_{10} (2.88 μm) and d_{90} (15.2 μm), suggesting a substantially finer particle size distribution. Differences are also apparent in the d_{50} values, where IBV reaches only 83.7 μm , while the other mixtures exceed 269 μm , indicating the presence of coarser particles in those formulations.

Fig. 3 graphically confirms these findings. The IBV exhibits a narrow distribution dominated by fine particles, whereas the other mixtures demonstrate broader particle size distributions with more pronounced peaks in the coarser fraction range. This granulometric profile can significantly affect flow properties and overall print quality: finer mixtures may provide better printing resolution, while broader distributions can enhance the mechanical performance of the final product due to higher densification potential after compaction.

In Direct Ink Writing (DIW) of ceramic pastes, particle size distribution plays a crucial role in shaping rheological behaviour, including viscosity, yield stress, and overall flow characteristics. These parameters directly influence print quality, layer stability, and the material's ability to pass through the nozzle without clogging.

Mixtures with higher proportions of fine particles (lower d_{10} and d_{90} values) are expected to exhibit increased viscosity and higher yield stress. Fine particles have a larger specific surface area, which leads to greater interparticle friction and stronger interactions with the binder

(e.g., water or organic additives), resulting in a denser and less fluid mixture. Conversely, the addition of coarser particles (higher d_{90}) can decrease the overall viscosity. Larger particles disrupt the close packing of the finer fraction, increasing the free volume and reducing interparticle friction. Mixtures such as IBV+RW2 or IBV+RW3, with d_{90} values exceeding 330 μm , are likely to demonstrate lower viscosity, which facilitates extrusion and reduces the risk of nozzle clogging. Based on these observations, the rheological properties of the analysed mixtures were further evaluated.

3.2. Rheological properties

Fig. 4 shows the dependence of viscosity on shear rate for the individual paste samples, presented as lines corresponding to the Power Law model. Table 4 summarizes the measured critical values at structural collapse (viscosity, shear rate, and shear stress), along with the corresponding Power Law model parameters. All samples exhibited a comparable tendency toward shear-thinning behaviour. Among them, the most pronounced shear-thinning effect was observed in the IBV sample, which had the lowest value of the power-law exponent b . In contrast, the IBV+RW2 sample showed the weakest shear-thinning behaviour, as indicated by the highest exponent b .

Based on the maximum measured critical shear stress (τ_c) and viscosity (η)—corresponding to the point of structural breakdown between the parallel plates under rotation (see Table 4)—the analysed mixtures can be classified into two groups with similar rheological profiles. From the perspective of printability and nozzle flowability, the IBV+RW1 and IBV+RW2 samples appear to be more suitable. These mixtures demonstrated lower internal resistance to flow, as confirmed by their lower τ_c and η values during testing. In contrast, IBV+RW3 and IBV samples exhibited higher viscosity and critical shear stress values, which may reflect greater mechanical stability of these materials under load. However, while the IBV+RW1 and IBV+RW2 mixtures offer improved extrudability, they may be more susceptible to structural collapse when exposed to higher mechanical stresses. Rheological parameters critical shear stress τ_c , viscosity η at structural failure, critical shear rate $\dot{\gamma}$ and power law parameters a , b and r are listed in Table 4 below.

Measuring the shear rate–viscosity relationship alone does not always provide sufficient insight into the complex rheological behaviour of a material during 3D printing. While viscosity characterizes the material's resistance to flow, it does not capture the interaction between the viscous and elastic components, which significantly influence layer stability after extrusion. Therefore, in addition to rotational testing, an oscillatory rheological test was employed to enable a more detailed characterization of the viscoelastic properties.

This test provides information not only on the loss modulus (G''), which relates to the material's flow behaviour, but also on the storage modulus (G'), which reflects the material's ability to maintain its shape. These parameters are crucial for predicting whether the material will remain stable after extrusion or tend to slump or deform. Thus, oscillatory testing represents a more comprehensive approach to printability evaluation, allowing optimization of both extrusion performance and the quality of the printed layers.

Fig. 5 shows the results of the Amplitude Sweep test for the individual mixtures. Table 5 presents the corresponding quantitative values, including the crossover points ($G' = G''$) in kPa, critical shear stress (τ_{cp}), and the boundaries of the linear viscoelastic region (LVR) expressed in terms of shear rate and shear stress.

The results of the Amplitude Sweep measurements allowed the tested mixtures to be categorized into two distinct groups based on their viscoelastic behaviour. The first group comprises the IBV+RW1 and IBV+RW2 samples, which exhibit higher crossover moduli ($G' = G''$) specifically 2319 Pa and 3227 Pa, respectively indicating a pronounced elastic character of these pastes. However, the transition from the linear to the nonlinear viscoelastic region, defined by the critical shear stress τ_{LVR} , occurs at relatively low shear stresses of 149.3 Pa and 75.8 Pa,

Table 3

Particle size distribution of raw materials and mixtures.

Sample	d_{10} (μm)	d_{50} (μm)	d_{90} (μm)
IBV	2.88	15.2	83.7
RW1	38.8	212	517
RW2	43.3	244	533
RW3	29.0	200	485
IBV+RW1	3.83	30.3	269
IBV+RW2	4.00	34.0	350
IBV+RW3	3.88	36.4	331

Fig. 3. Particle size distribution of mixtures and base IBV matrix.

Fig. 4. Power Law models from Shear rate vs. Shear viscosity measurement.

Table 4
Rheological parameters of samples.

Sample	τ_c (Pa)	η (Pa·s)	γ (s ⁻¹)	a (-)	b (-)	r (-)
IBV+RW1	1190	6182	0.1924	2474	-0.7217	0.9997
IBV+RW2	1023	3116	0.3282	2606	-0.6843	0.9995
IBV+RW3	2802	17,380	0.1612	5286	-0.7313	0.9995
IBV	2196	23,420	0.09375	4567	-0.7574	0.9999

respectively. The second group, consisting of IBV+RW3 and IBV, shows lower crossover moduli 1481 Pa and 1667 Pa, indicating reduced elasticity in the linear region. Nonetheless, these mixtures reach significantly higher critical shear stress values τ_{cp} (1516 Pa and 1848 Pa) and higher τ_{LVR} values (284.1 Pa and 396.4 Pa). This suggests that although they are less elastic, they demonstrate greater resistance to shear deformation and thus offer superior structural stability under mechanical loading during printing.

This classification is in line with the shear rate–viscosity measurements, where IBV+RW3 and IBV also displayed higher viscosity and

critical shear stress, further confirming their higher internal cohesion and resistance to flow. From a practical standpoint, this implies that while IBV+RW1 and IBV+RW2 mixtures are more suitable for easy nozzle flow, the IBV+RW3 and IBV mixtures are better at maintaining shape after extrusion and may offer greater layer stability during the stacking process. Among the tested formulations, the IBV+RW3 mixture appears to be the most suitable candidate for 3D printing of ceramic structures using recycled materials in terms of mechanical stability under the load of successive layers. It exhibited the highest critical shear stress τ_{cp} , which is comparable to the reference sample IBV, i.e., pure clay. This indicates high mechanical stability despite the presence of recycled refractory components. Conversely, in terms of extrudability while maintaining structural integrity, IBV+RW1 appears to be the most favourable formulation. It shows lower viscosity, stronger shear-thinning behaviour, and a relatively high τ_{LVR} , indicating a favourable balance between printability and mechanical resistance during extrusion.

4. Conclusion

The conducted rheological measurements confirmed that all tested mixtures exhibit shear-thinning behaviour, with the most pronounced effect observed in the IBV formulation. Based on rotational and oscillatory tests, the mixtures could be classified into two groups according to their viscoelastic properties and mechanical stability. The IBV+RW1 and IBV+RW2 mixtures demonstrated lower viscosity and lower critical shear stress, indicating better extrudability but reduced resistance to mechanical loading during layer stacking. In contrast, the IBV+RW3 and IBV samples reached higher values of critical shear stress (τ_{cp}) and LVR limits (τ_{LVR}), suggesting greater structural stability after extrusion. The IBV+RW3 mixture exhibited the highest mechanical stability, with rheological performance comparable to that of pure clay (IBV). The IBV+RW1 mixture was identified as optimal in terms of balancing good nozzle flow with sufficient post-extrusion stability. Additionally, the bulk density of the filler significantly influenced the rheological behaviour the lower density of RW3 resulted in a higher solid particle fraction in the mixture, which contributed to increased viscosity and yield stress. Further research will focus on the mechanical and structural properties of clay–refractory waste ceramics before and after firing of DIW-printed structures.

In addition to rheological characterization, preliminary extrusion trials were conducted under laboratory conditions to qualitatively assess the extrusion behaviour and structural stability of the tested mixtures. Mixtures with lower viscosity and critical shear stress (IBV+RW1, IBV+RW2) showed smooth extrusion and good layer deposition, but

Fig. 5. Oscillatory test results; (a) IBV+RW1, (b) IBV+RW2, (c) IBV+RW3, (d) IBV.

Table 5
Crossover points and end of LVR parameters for measured samples.

Sample	$G' = G''$ (Pa)	τ_{cp} (Pa)	$\dot{\gamma}_{LVR}$ (s^{-1})	τ_{LVR} (Pa)
IBV+RW1	2319	584.3	0.0003893	149.3
IBV+RW2	3227	463.8	0.0001826	75.8
IBV+RW3	1481	1516	0.0003444	284.1
IBV	1667	1848	0.0004919	396.4

their stability under higher loads was limited, leading to partial deformation in taller structures. In contrast, mixtures with higher viscosity and yield stress (IBV+RW3, IBV) exhibited superior shape stability and dimensional accuracy during layer stacking, although extrusion required higher pressure. These observations are consistent with the classification of mixtures into two rheological behaviour groups (see Fig. 4). A systematic evaluation of the direct correlation between rheological properties and printing performance, including shape fidelity, dimensional accuracy, and mechanical strength after drying/firing—is highly relevant. This topic is currently being addressed in a follow-up study, which will investigate rheology and printability

relationships in detail. These rheological data confirm the applicability of recycled materials for 3D printing. These findings underline the practical relevance of rheological characterization for extrusion-based additive manufacturing.

Funding

This research received no external funding.

Data availability

The data used in this study is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15861501>.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jiří Rozbroj: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. David Žurovec: Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Project administration. Jakub Hlosta: Conceptualization,

Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration. **Michaela Topinková**: Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Hana Ovčáčková**: Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Jan Diviš**: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Project administration. **Kamila Pokorná**: Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **Jan Nečas**: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Jiří Zegzulka**: Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

This paper was created as part of the project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004631 Materials and technologies for sustainable development within the Jan Amos Komenský Operational Program financed by the European Union and from the state budget of the Czech Republic, and project The European Just Transition Fund supported this work within the Operational Programme Just Transition under the aegis of the Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic, project CirkArena, number CZ.10.03.01/00/22_003/0000045. Work was also supported by Grant of SGS No. SP2025/005 Development of measuring apparatus for determination of thermodynamic properties of mineral raw materials for design of process and treatment plants, Faculty of Mining and Geology, VSB - Technical University Ostrava, Czech Republic.

References

- [1] J. Bonilla-Cruz, M.A. Ávila-López, F.E.L. Rodríguez, A. Aguilar-Elguezabal, T. E. Lara-Ceniceros, 3D printable ceramic pastes design: correlating rheology & printability, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 42 (13) (2022) 6033–6039.
- [2] Daniel A. RAU, Christopher B. WILLIAMS, Michael J BORTNER, Rheology and printability: a survey of critical relationships for direct ink write materials design, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* (2023) 101188.
- [3] Shareen SL Chan, et al., 3D printing of clay for decorative architectural applications: effect of solids volume fraction on rheology and printability, *Addit. Manuf.* 35 (2020) 101335.
- [4] C.F. Revelo, H.A. Colorado, 3D printing of kaolinite clay ceramics using the Direct Ink Writing (DIW) technique, *Ceram. Int.* 44 (5) (2018) 5673–5682.
- [5] B. Gyawali, R. Haghazari, P. Akula, K. Alba, V. Nasir, A review on 3D printing with clay and sawdust/natural fibers: printability, rheology, properties, and applications, *Results Eng.* (2024) 103024.
- [6] S. Bose, E.K. Akdogan, V.K. Balla, S. Ciliveri, P. Colombo, G. Franchin, A. Bandyopadhyay, 3D printing of ceramics: advantages, challenges, applications, and perspectives, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 107 (12) (2024) 7879–7920.
- [7] P.B. Chandan, M.R. Sankar, Tailoring the proportion of particle size to evaluate extrusion-based 3D printed alumina ceramics, *Mater. Sci. Eng.: B* 314 (2025) 117984.
- [8] K. Ryu, J. Kim, J. Choi, U. Kim, The 3D printing behavior of photocurable ceramic/polymer composite slurries prepared with different particle sizes, *Nanomaterials* 12 (15) (2022) 2631.
- [9] C. Ancy, H. Jorrot, Yield stress for particle suspensions within a clay dispersion, *J. Rheol. (N N Y)* 45 (2) (2001) 297–319.
- [10] M.G. Rasteiro, I. Salgueiros, Rheology of particulate suspensions in ceramic industry, *Part. Sci. Technol.* 23 (2) (2005) 145–157.
- [11] L. del-Mazo-Barbara, M.P. Ginebra, Rheological characterisation of ceramic inks for 3D direct ink writing: a review, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 41 (16) (2021) 18–33.
- [12] R.D. Corder, Y.J. Chen, P. Pibulchinda, J.P. Youngblood, A.M. Ardekani, K.A. Erk, Rheology of 3D printable ceramic suspensions: effects of non-adsorbing polymer on discontinuous shear thickening, *Soft Matter* 19 (5) (2023) 882–891.
- [13] R.L. Walton, E.R. Kupp, G.L. Messing, Additive manufacturing of textured ceramics: a review, *J. Mater. Res.* 36 (2021) 3591–3606.
- [14] S. Fournier, J. Chevalier, S. Perez-Robles, C. Carotenuto, M. Minale, H. Reveron, G. P. Baeza, Spreading ceramic stereolithography pastes: insights from shear-and orthogonal-rheology, *J. Rheol. (N N Y)* 68 (1) (2024) 83–97.
- [15] R. Chen, A. Bratten, J. Rittenhouse, T. Huang, W. Jia, M.C. Leu, H. Wen, Additive manufacturing of complexly shaped SiC with high density via extrusion-based technique—Effects of slurry thixotropic behavior and 3D printing parameters, *Ceram. Int.* 48 (19) (2022) 28444–28454.
- [16] I.L. de Camargo, M.M. Morais, C.A. Fortulan, M.C. Branciforti, A review on the rheological behavior and formulations of ceramic suspensions for vat photopolymerization, *Ceram. Int.* 47 (9) (2021) 11906–11921.
- [17] H.A. Barnes, Thixotropy—A review, *J Nonnewt. Fluid Mech.* 70 (1–2) (1997) 1–33.
- [18] F. Zhang, Z. Li, M. Xu, S. Wang, N. Li, J. Yang, A review of 3D printed porous ceramics, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 42 (8) (2022) 3351–3373.
- [19] T. Chen, A. Sun, C. Chu, H. Wu, J. Wang, G. Xu, Rheological behavior of titania ink and mechanical properties of titania ceramic structures by 3D direct ink writing using high solid loading titania ceramic ink, *J. Alloys Compd.* 783 (2019) 321–328.
- [20] K. Huang, H. Elsayed, G. Franchin, P. Colombo, Complex SiOC ceramics from 2D structures by 3D printing and origami, *Addit. Manuf.* 33 (2020) 101144.
- [21] S. Przybyła, M. Kwiatkowski, M. Kwiatkowski, M. Hebda, Optimization of ceramic paste composition for 3D printing via robocasting, *Materials* 17 (18) (2024) 4560.
- [22] Q. Cai, S. Meille, J. Chevalier, S. Zhou, F. Bouville, I. Tirichenko, E. Saiz, 3D-printing of ceramic filaments with ductile metallic cores, *Mater. Des.* 225 (2023) 111463.
- [23] X. Xu, J. Zhang, P. Jiang, D. Liu, X. Jia, X. Wang, F. Zhou, Direct ink writing of aluminum-phosphate-bonded Al₂O₃ ceramic with ultra-low dimensional shrinkage, *Ceram. Int.* 48 (1) (2022) 864–871.
- [24] E. Feilden, E.G.T. Blanca, F. Giuliani, E. Saiz, L. Vandeperre, Robocasting of structural ceramic parts with hydrogel inks, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 36 (10) (2016) 2525–2533.
- [25] S.H. Ji, D.S. Kim, M.S. Park, D. Lee, J.S. Yun, Development of multicolor 3D-printed 3Y-ZrO₂ sintered bodies by optimizing rheological properties of UV-curable high-content ceramic nanocomposites, *Mater. Des.* 209 (2021) 109981.
- [26] Y. Yang, D. Cai, Z. Yang, X. Duan, P. He, D. Jia, Y. Zhou, Rheology of organics-free aqueous ceramic suspensions for additive manufacturing of dense silicon nitride ceramics, *Ceram. Int.* 48 (21) (2022) 31941–31951.
- [27] L. Tabard, V. Garnier, E. Prud'Homme, E.J. Courtial, S. Meille, J. Adrien, L. Gremillard, Robocasting of highly porous ceramics scaffolds with hierarchized porosity, *Addit. Manuf.* 38 (2021) 101776.
- [28] T. An, K.T. Hwang, J.H. Kim, J. Kim, Extrusion-based 3D direct ink writing of NiZn-ferrite structures with viscoelastic ceramic suspension, *Ceram. Int.* 46 (5) (2020) 6469–6476.
- [29] S. Wu, X. Xu, Y. Wang, P. Jiang, J. Wu, X. Jia, Z. Ji, Coaxial 3D printed Al₂O₃ ceramic continuous-flow fixed-bed reactor with bionic core-shell structure, *Ceram. Int.* 50 (8) (2024) 13662–13670.
- [30] X. Zhang, W. Huo, J. Liu, Y. Zhang, S. Zhang, J. Yang, 3D printing boehmite gel foams into lightweight porous ceramics with hierarchical pore structure, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 40 (3) (2020) 930–934.
- [31] T. Tu, G. Jiang, SiC reticulated porous ceramics by 3D printing, gelcasting and liquid drying, *Ceram. Int.* 44 (3) (2018) 3400–3405.
- [32] A.L. Troksa, H.V. Eshelman, S. Chandrasekaran, N. Rodríguez, S. Ruelas, E. B. Duoss, P.G. Campbell, 3D-printed nanoporous ceramics: tunable feedstock for direct ink write and projection microstereolithography, *Mater. Des.* 198 (2021) 109337.
- [33] R. Wu, T. Zeng, M. Fan, Y. Cui, G. Xu, X. Wang, S. Cheng, Microstructure and mechanical properties of 3D printed porous Al₂O₃-ZrO₂ laminated ceramics with tailored porosity, *Ceram. Int.* 49 (20) (2023) 33369–33381.
- [34] Vlček, J.; Ovčáčková, H.; Velička, M.; Topinková, M.; Burda, J.; Matějková, P. The corrosion effect of fly ash from biomass combustion on Andalusite refractory materials. *Minerals* 2023, 13, 357. <https://doi.org/10.3390/min13030357>.
- [35] J. Poirier, F. Qafssaoui, J.P. Ildefonse, M.L. Bouchetou, Analysis and interpretation of refractory microstructure in studies of corrosion mechanisms by liquid oxides, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 28 (2008) 1557–1568 (H1).
- [36] Classification of Dense Shaped Refractory Products—Part 1: Alumina-Silica; ČSN EN ISO 10080-1: ČSN EN ISO 10 081-1, Czech Stadrdrts Institute, Praha, Czech Republic, 2005.